

A ROLE OF INTERFACE STRUCTURE FOR SUPERIOR PLASTIC DEFORMATION IN Al-Mg-Si ALLOY COMPOSITES CONTAINING CERAMICS REINFORCEMENTS

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Abstract

Large elongation in Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si composite has been correlated to the presence of a reaction phase at interfaces between Si₃N₄w crystals and the Al-matrix during the tensile deformation. Strong reaction at interfaces between Si₃N₄w crystals and the Al-matrix occurs in the Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si composite, which shows a large elongation. On the other hand, no evidence for an interfacial reaction between the Al-matrix and both reinforcements of SiCw and TiO₂w crystals in SiCw/Al-Mg-Si and TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si composites, which show much lower elongation, was observed.

1 Introduction

In the last decades, some aluminum alloy composites reinforced with Si₃N₄(1-4) or SiC(5-7), which fabricated by the powder metallurgy method, have been studied, because it has been demonstrated that the possibility of superplastic forming exhibits in the fine-grained aluminum alloy-matrix composites. It was initially pointed out by Nieh and Wadsworth (8) and Nieh, Wadsworth and Imai (9) that a fine grain size is a necessary but insufficient condition for the observed high strain rate superplastic phenomenon. That is, not all alloys of fine grain size (~1μm) containing very fine ceramics-reinforcements exhibit high strain rate superplasticity. It was further pointed out that the observed high strain rate superplastic phenomenon may be related to the presence of liquid phases at interfaces or grain boundaries.

It is well revealed that some aluminum alloy-matrix composites, which showed large elongation at high-strain-rate above 10⁻² s⁻¹, have reaction phases at interfaces between the Al-matrix and ceramic reinforcements (10). The investigation results suggest that Mg from Al-matrix is enriched at the interfaces between the Al-matrix and Si₃N₄w crystal during the extrusion process,

because the interfaces are concentration places of dislocations, which probably trap and convey Mg atoms. The enrich regions of Mg at the interfaces serve as starting points for the reaction between Si₃N₄w crystals and the Al-matrix, and consequently the reaction products include Mg and Si. The concentration of Mg and Si in the Al solid solution lowers the melting point of the regions near interfaces and finally produces partial liquid regions around the interfaces at the deformation temperature. Stress concentration during strong deformation occurs at the interfaces between the ceramics with poor ductility and ductile metal matrix, and finally leads to failure. In the same way, it is suggested that the local liquid regions appear at the interfaces between Si₃N₄w crystals and the Al-matrix during superplastic deformation, and serve to relieve the stress concentrations caused by grain boundary sliding and thereby limits extensive development of internal cavitations.

The objective, in the present study, is to reveal closely the effect of the interface condition in the Al-Mg-Si alloy composites containing different ceramics reinforcements, which maybe related strongly to superior plastic flow, through the comparing of two kind of composites, which depending on whether they show superior plastic flow or not.

2 Materials and Experimental Procedure

The composites used in this work are Al-Mg-Si alloy (6061Al) reinforced with 20 vol.% Si₃N₄, SiC and TiO₂ whiskers, respectively. The chemical composition of Al-Mg-Si alloy is following as 1.3Mg-0.75Si-0.47Fe-0.39Cu-0.15Cr-Al(wt.%). The composites were prepared by ultra-sonically mixing the Al-Mg-Si alloy powders and the reinforcements in an alcohol solvent, drying and compressing in vacuum for 1.2 ks under a pressure of 390 MPa at 873 K. The sintered bodies were extruded with a reduction

ratio of 100:1 at 773 K. The details of fabrication procedure are given elsewhere (11). The extruded samples were tensile tested to investigate plasticity. The tensile testing condition, properties and characteristics of these composites are summarized in table 1.

Table1. Specifications of the Al-Mg-Si alloy composites.

Composite	Grain size	Ei(s ⁻¹)	T(K)	El.(%)(Max.)
6061/Si3N4	2	2 × 10 ⁻¹	818	680
6061/SiCw	2	3 × 10 ⁻¹	818	60
6061/TiO2w	2	2 × 10 ⁻¹	818	20

The tensile tested samples were cut into thin slices, perpendicular to the extrusion axis. The slices were mechanically polished to a thickness of about 30 μm, and were punched out to 3 mm diameter discs by an ultra-sonic cutter. The disc-shaped samples were thinned with argon ions at an accelerating voltage of 3 kV with a glancing angles of 10 ~ 20 degrees. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and high-resolution electron microscopy (HREM) observations were performed using a 400 kV electron microscope (JEM-4000EX) with a resolution of 0.17 nm. Chemical analysis of the precipitates at interfaces were made with a 300 kV electron microscope (JEM-3000EX) equipped with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). The probe sizes used for the EDS analysis were 3 ~ 5 nm.

3 Results

Figure 1(a) shows a Typical TEM image of the tensile-tested SiCw/Al-Mg-Si specimen, which was deformed to failure (60 %) at a strain rate of 3 × 10⁻² s⁻¹ and at 818 K. In the image (Fig. 1(a)), a relatively uniform distribution of SiCw crystals is observed. Figure 1 (b) shows a HRTEM image of the interface region indicated by a rectangle in figure 1 (b).

Fig.1. (a) Typical TEM image, (b) HRTEM image of an interface between the Al-matrix and SiCw.

The HRTEM image shows that the (200) plane of the Al-matrix is bonded directly with (002) plane of a SiCw crystal, and that there is no reaction at interface between the Al-matrix and SiCw crystal during the tensile deformation.

Similar results were obtained in the tensile-tested TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si sample. Figure 2(a) shows a Typical TEM image of the tensile-tested TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si specimen, which was deformed to failure (20 %) at a strain rate of 2 × 10⁻¹ s⁻¹ and at 818 K. In the image (Fig. 2(a)), TiO₂w crystals are unevenly distributed, an agglomeration of TiO₂w crystals is observed in the matrix, as indicated by arrows.

Figure 2 (b) is a TEM image of a TiO₂w crystal embedded in the Al-matrix in the tensile-tested TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si specimen, and a HRTEM image of the interface region indicated by a rectangle in figure 2 (b). As can be seen in figure 2 (b), the (111) plane of the Al-matrix is bonded directly with the (210) plane of a TiO₂w crystal without any reactants and impurities (for example: amorphous etc.) at interfaces between TiO₂w crystal and the Al-matrix.

This result also indicates that no reaction between the Al-matrix and TiO₂w crystal occurred in the TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si composites during the tensile deformation.

Fig.2. (a) Typical TEM image, (b) HRTEM image of an interface between the Al-matrix and TiO₂w.

4 Discussions

Maximum elongations as a function of strain rate for as-extruded Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si, SiCw/Al-Mg-Si and TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si composites are shown in figure 3. The tensile tests for the above composites were conducted under a range of strain rate from 1 × 10⁻³ to 9 × 10² and at 818 K. The as-tensile tested SiCw/Al-Mg-Si and TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si composites showed a relatively low tensile ductility with the maximum elongations of 60% and 20%, respectively, which are considerably much lower than the typical elongation of several hundred percentages of conventional superplastic composite materials.

Fig.3. Maximum elongations as a function of strain rate for as-extruded Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si, SiCw/Al-Mg-Si and TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si composites.

In the figure 1 (b), one can see that no reaction at interfaces between the Al-matrix and SiCw crystal occurs for the tensile-tested SiCw/Al-Mg-Si specimen. EDS analysis revealed that no solute concentration occurred at interfaces between the Al-matrix and SiCw crystal in the SiCw/Al-Mg-Si composite. Figure 4 (a) and (b) show typical TEM and HRTEM images of an interface in the tensile-tested SiCw/Al-Mg-Si specimen, and the numbered places (in Fig.4(b)) at which EDS analyses were carried out. Analytical data for these sampling points are listed in table 2.

Fig.4. (a)TEM image of a SiCw/Al matrix interface, (b)HRTEM image of the region indicated by the rectangle in Fig.4(a).

Table 2. EDS data at the sampling points in Fig.4.

Sample number	domains	Al	Mg	Si	Cu	Fe	Cr
1	Al matrix	98.5	0.3	1.2	-	-	-
2	Interface	55.9	-	43.4	0.7	-	-
3	SiCw	2.0	-	98.0	-	-	-

A similar result is obtained in the tensile tested TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si specimen. The TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si specimen, which showed no reaction between the Al-matrix and TiO₂w crystal, exhibits a much

lower elongation of 20%.

On the other hand, TEM observations of the tensile-tested Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si composites show considerable differences in the interface structure from those of the tensile tested Al-Mg-Si alloy composites reinforced with SiCw and TiO₂w crystals. Figure 5 shows a typical TEM image of the tensile-tested Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si specimen, which was deformed to failure (620 %) at a high initial strain rate of $2 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 818 K.

Fig.5. Typical TEM image of the tensile tested Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si specimen.

The inspection of the photograph shows that the Si₃N₄ reinforcements are reasonably homogeneously dispersed in the matrix, and the average grain sizes of the matrix in Si₃N₄/Al-Mg-Si specimen are about 2 ~ 3 µm, which are almost the same as those of the SiCw/Al-Mg-Si and TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si specimens. Figure 6 (a) and 6 (b) show TEM and HRTEM images of the interfaces between the metal matrix and Si₃N₄w crystals in the tensile tested Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si specimen, respectively.

Fig.6. (a)TEM image of a Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si interface, (b)HRTEM image of the region indicated by the rectangle in Fig.6(a).

The Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si specimen, which showed high strain rate superplasticity, is observed to have reaction phases at interfaces between the Al-matrix and Si₃N₄w crystal. In the previous works (10, 13), it is already revealed that the reaction between the Al-matrix and ceramics reinforcements occurred during the extrusion

process at 773 K, and further it was enhanced during the tensile-testing process at 818 K. From the above observations in SiCw/Al-Mg-Si and TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si specimens, it is supposed that reaction phases at interfaces between the Al-matrix and ceramics reinforcements are required for developing superior plasticity.

In the present work, it is confirmed that the high-strain-rate superplasticity in aluminum alloy matrix composites is related strongly to interface structures. That is, the composites exhibiting high-strain-rate superplasticity have reaction phases at interfaces. Although conclusive processes on interfacial reaction could not be determined in the present work, the experimental results revealed that the surface condition of ceramics reinforcements undoubtedly gives an important role on interfacial reaction in the high-strain-rate superplastic Al alloy matrix composites. Therefore, it might be argued that the formation of interfacial reactants is likely to concern with amorphous SiO₂ layer, because of the presence of amorphous SiO₂ layers on Si₃N₄w crystals in the Al alloy matrix composites containing Si₃N₄ whiskers.

5 Conclusions

The influence of different kinds of ceramics reinforcements on interface structures and high strain rate superplasticity were investigated for the SiCw/Al, TiO₂w/Al and Si₃N₄w/Al composites. The results are summarized as follows.

No reaction at interfaces between the Al-matrix and both SiCw and TiO₂w was observed in the tensile tested SiCw/Al-Mg-Si and TiO₂w/Al-Mg-Si specimens, which showed much low elongations of 60% and 20%, respectively.

On the other hand, strong reaction at interfaces was observed in the tensile-tested Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si specimen, which showed a high elongation of 620 % at a high strain rate of $2 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 818 K.

It is concluded that superplastic phenomenon of the Si₃N₄w/Al-Mg-Si composite is concerned with an existence of reactants at interfaces between the Al-matrix and Si₃N₄w crystal.

6 References

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